

PROPER DIAGNOSIS OF THE DISEASE AND FURTHER TREATMENT OF B12-DEFICIENCY ANEMIA

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Abstract: In B12-deficiency anemia, the syndrome of damage to the nervous system dominates, which naturally forces them to seek help from a neurologist. In these cases, the correct diagnosis of the disease and further treatment depend on the latter, since the hasty administration of vitamin B12 very quickly leads to the disappearance of megaloblasts from the bone marrow, which are a pathognomonic sign of pernicious anemia. This makes it difficult to recognize the true nature of neurological disorders. Unfortunately, it should be recognized that to date, the neurological manifestations of B12-deficiency anemia have not been systematized and do not have a clear description.

Keywords: vitamin B12, anemia, neurological syndrome, bone marrow.

The aim of the study was to study the frequency and nature of neurological manifestations of B12-deficiency anemia. 52 patients were observed, of which 30 (57%) had neurological manifestations of funicular myelosis. Sensitivity disorders, changes in Achilles and knee reflexes, and gait disorders were most often detected. The complete disappearance of neurological manifestations of B12-deficient anemia is possible only with a mild degree of funicular myelosis.

Key words: B12-deficiency anemia, funicular myelosis.

Materials and methods: for 7 years, 52 patients with newly diagnosed B12 deficiency anemia (20 men, 32 women, average age - 64.3 years) were examined together with hematologists. The diagnosis was clinically verified and confirmed by a bone marrow punctate examination. It should be specially noted that megaloblasts were found in all patients in the bone marrow punctate. All patients underwent a thorough neurological examination, involving electroencephalography (18 patients), electroneuromyography-magnetic resonance or computed tomography (10), esophagogastroduodenoscopy (29), if necessary. According to the classification of P.M. Alperin and Yu.G. Miterev [1], anemia of mild severity (HH -110-90 g/l) was present in 13 patients, moderate (HH-89-70 g/l) - in 29 and severe anemia (HH - 69 g/l and below) - in 10 patients. It should be noted that among the examined patients there were no strict vegetarians, patients who had undergone gastrectomy, suffering from Crohn's disease, helminthic invasion (diphyllobothriosis), people taking medications for a long time (aminosalicylic acid, neomycin, etc.), as well as those treated with vitamin B12 injections. This made it possible to exclude the symptomatic nature of B12-deficient anemia and its cytologically unconfirmed variants.

Results and their discussion. When examining patients, the straw-yellow coloration of the skin and sclera attracted attention (38; 73%). At the same time, the frequency of detection of this symptom clearly increased with increasing severity of anemia. Normal body mass index (18.5-24.9 kg/m²) was found in 29 patients, decreased (<18.5 kg/m²) in one, increased (>25.0 kg/m²) in 22 patients. This corresponds to the observations of L.I. Idelson [4] and generally

indicates that exhaustion among patients with B12 deficiency anemia, despite the presence of severe disease, is relatively rare.

Changes from the gastrointestinal tract were present in most patients and were quite specific. Thus, complaints of severity or pain in the epigastric region, belching, nausea, decreased appetite as subjective manifestations of atrophic gastritis were present in 37 (71.1%) patients. The latter was confirmed by esophagogastroduodenoscopy and mucosal biopsy. Of particular note is the presence in some patients of glossitis (Gunther's tongue; 19; 36.5%) - a crimson-colored tongue with smoothed papillae ("varnished"). In some patients (8; 15.4%), in addition, there were areas of inflammation with erosions at the tip and edges of the tongue. The spleen was palpated in 13 (25%) patients, and an increase in liver size was observed in 10 (19.2%) patients. On the part of the cardiovascular system, there was an expansion of the boundaries of relative cardiac dullness to the left (by 1-2 cm), a tendency to tachycardia (average heart rate - 79.8 in 1 min) and arterial hypotension (110/70 -100/60 mmHg).

Hyperchromic (43; 82.7%), less often normochromic anemia (9; 17.3%), moderate leukopenia and thrombocytopenia were usually detected in the blood of the examined patients. On the part of erythrocytes, anisocytosis, macrocytosis and the presence of nuclear residues (Jolly corpuscles and Kebot rings) were noted. The number of reticulocytes was reduced or normal. Erythrocytes were often detected. Irritation of the red germ was detected in the bone marrow, and megaloblasts, a characteristic sign of pernicious anemia, were also detected.

Based on the submitted complaints and the results of an objective neurological examination, all patients were divided into 2 groups. Group 1 included 22 (43%) patients who complained of general weakness, shortness of breath during exercise, fatigue, dizziness, i.e. complaints characteristic of anemia, but they did not have subjective and objective signs indicating damage to the nervous system. It should be noted that the majority of these patients (18) initially turned to a therapist.

Group 2 included 30 (57%) patients who, along with the above complaints, also had subjective and objective manifestations typical of funicular myelosis. It should be noted that if patients of the 1st group complained of general weakness, then patients of the 2nd, as a rule, added to this that they were mainly concerned about weakness in their legs and arms.

A comparison of patients in groups 1 and 2, depending on the severity of anemia, did not reveal any pattern. Thus, anemia of mild severity was present in groups 1 and 2, respectively, in 5 and 7 cases, moderate in 13 and 16, and severe anemia in 4 and 6 cases. A similar situation has been noted by other researchers [1, 3, 4]. This suggests that the main role in the occurrence of neurological manifestations of pernicious anemia is played not so much by the severity of anemia as by its duration. However, it is always difficult for a doctor to judge the duration of this pathology. Usually, patients adapt well to gradually increasing anemia and turn to a doctor when their compensatory capabilities are exhausted or when neurological disorders appear. And further, as the above data indicate, the appearance of signs of damage to the nervous system is not an obligate manifestation of B12-deficiency anemia. They occur only in 57% of patients and, apparently, some additional conditions are necessary for their appearance, and not only vitamin B deficiency itself. The frequency of subjective and objective neurological disorders detected in 30 patients with pernicious anemia is presented in

Of particular interest are the patients of the 2nd group, among whom, by the way, 12 patients initially turned to a neurologist for help.

Conclusions: It must be said that neurologists saw the unusual condition of the patient, in which the neurological symptoms as a whole did not correspond to that characteristic of a "banal" lesion of the nervous system. This forced them to refrain from the standard vitamin B12 prescription, continue the examination and eventually make the correct diagnosis.

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